

FUZZY ADAPTIVE CPM-PERT METHOD

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Abstract: This paper presents a novel methodology for assessing the criticality of project paths and activities within a fuzzy logic framework. The proposed approach integrates the relative degree of criticality and the agreement index into a unified indicator, offering a more precise and comprehensive measure of criticality. Research findings indicate that the fuzzy adaptive CPM-PERT method can be effectively applied in project planning. Its application is particularly suitable for the construction industry, where activity durations and cost estimates are often subject to a high degree of uncertainty and subjectivity.

Keywords: Project planning, Fuzzy, CPM, PERT, Critical Degree.

1. INTRODUCTION

Project management in construction is a complex task, filled with uncertainty and risks. The planned project completion time is often not met, leading to delays in the scheduled construction period. Quality planning includes a realistic assessment of the optimal balance between time, available resources, and construction costs. Scientists and researchers have devoted most of their attention to improving the most popular project planning methods: the Critical Path Method (CPM) and the Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT), which consider activity durations as deterministic or probabilistic values, respectively.

Activity durations are imprecise and vague because they are mostly estimated by experts based on their experience. For this reason, the use of fuzzy set theory is proposed for modeling uncertainty instead of probabilistic methods in network planning theory, resulting in new, modified project planning methods, the most well-known of which are the Fuzzy Critical Path Method (FCPM) and the Fuzzy PERT Method (FPERT). This paper presents a new modified method called the Fuzzy Adaptive CPM-PERT, designed for improved project planning under uncertainty.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The theory of fuzzy sets (Fuzzy Set Theory) is an alternative approach for handling uncertainty in activity durations. Fuzzy logic measures imprecision or vagueness in estimation and may be preferable to probability theory in situations where historical data on activity durations is unavailable or unreliable (Liberatore, 2016).

Planning in cases where the duration of activities or project costs are given as fuzzy numbers is particularly suitable for application in construction, considering the high level of subjectivity that arises during the estimation of construction activities (Bakri et al. 2013).

In this paper, activity durations are represented using triangular fuzzy numbers $Ft(a, b, c)$, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Triangular fuzzy number $A = (a, b, c)$

The triangular fuzzy number $A = (a, b, c)$ has a membership function $\mu_A(x): \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined as follows:

$$\mu_A(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < a \\ \frac{x-a}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b}, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 0, & x > c \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The values $a, b,$ and c represent real numbers that satisfy the condition $a > 0$ and $a \leq b \leq c$.

Below are the basic arithmetic operations of addition, subtraction, and multiplication on triangular fuzzy numbers $A = (a_1, b_1, c_1)$ and $B = (a_2, b_2, c_2)$ (Dubois & Prade, 1978).

$$A + B = (a_1, b_1, c_1) + (a_2, b_2, c_2) = (a_1 + a_2, b_1 + b_2, c_1 + c_2) \quad (2)$$

$$A - B = (a_1, b_1, c_1) - (a_2, b_2, c_2) = (a_1 - a_2, b_1 - b_2, c_1 - c_2) \quad (3)$$

$$A \times B = (a_1, b_1, c_1) \times (a_2, b_2, c_2) = (a_1 \times a_2, b_1 \times b_2, c_1 \times c_2) \quad (3)$$

$$k \times A = k \times (a_1, b_1, c_1) = (k \times a_1, k \times b_1, k \times c_1) \quad (4)$$

Defuzzification is the process of representing a fuzzy set with a specific number, i.e., a fuzzy (uncertain) number is expressed as a deterministic (clear or “crisp”) number, that is, a real number. In project management, input data can be represented by fuzzy numbers; however, it is often required that the output data (e.g., project duration) be a clear “crisp” number.

There are several methods that enable defuzzification, and the most commonly used are: the maximum method, the center of area method, the mean of maximum method, the bisector method, the smallest of maximum method, etc. The choice of which method to apply depends on the nature of the problem the fuzzy model is intended to solve. The most frequently used defuzzification method is the *Center of Area (COA)* method, which determines the center of the area of a fuzzy set or fuzzy number (Shaheen et al., 2007). In the literature, another name for the COA method can be found, which is the *Center of Gravity (COG)* method.

Defuzzification of a fuzzy number using the COA (Center of Area) method is performed using the following formula (Moselhi, 2015):

$$y^* = \frac{\int x \cdot \mu_i(x) dx}{\int \mu_i(x) dx} \quad (5)$$

where is:

y^*	clear "crisp" number, obtained by defuzzification of a fuzzy number
μ	membership function of the fuzzy number
x	output variable

$$E(A) = \frac{a+2b+c}{4} \quad (6)$$

$$Var(A) = \sigma^2(A) = \frac{a^2+b^2+c^2-ab-ac-bc}{18} \quad (7)$$

The use of fuzzy numbers in project planning facilitates the project planner in defining activity durations. Activity durations do not need to be expressed as simple deterministic (“crisp”) values, as is typically the case in traditional project planning methods. For example, the project planner does not have to express their subjective estimate that an activity will last approximately 15 days as a crisp number (15); instead, it can be represented using a triangular fuzzy number (10, 15, 20). The planner can determine a confidence interval and estimate the duration as “approximately between 13 and 18 days,” which can also be modeled using the triangular fuzzy number (10, 15, 20).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the first phase of the experiment, fuzzy durations of activities were determined. First, it is necessary to define the list of activities with their mutual relationships in the network diagram and to define the fuzzy durations of the activities. This study will use a small project consisting of 10 activities, whose network plan is shown in Figure 2, while the durations of the activities and their interdependencies are

presented in Table 1. For simplicity of calculations, a “finish-to-start” (FS) relationship between activities is assumed.

Figure 2: Project Network Diagram

Table 1: PERT activity durations

Activity	PA	NA	Activity durations according to PERT						Critical activity
			t_o	t_m	t_p	t_e	σ	σ^2	
1		2,3,4	3	4	7	4.33	0.67	0.44	yes
2	1	5	4	5	7	5.17	0.5	0.25	
3	1	7	11	14	18	14.17	1.17	1.361	yes
4	1	6	2	5	7	4.83	0.83	0.694	
5	2	8	5	7	10	7.17	0.83	0.694	
6	4	7	4	6	8	6	0.67	0.444	
7	3,6	9	8	12	14	11.67	1	1	yes
8	5	9	2	4	6	4	0.67	0.444	
9	7,8	10	11	14	18	14.17	1.17	1.361	yes
10	9		8	10	12	10	0.67	0.444	yes
For the critical path Σ						54.33	4.67	4.611	

Meaning of the symbols in Table 1: PA – Predecessor activity; NA – Successor activity; t_o – Optimistic duration; t_m – Most likely duration; t_p – Pessimistic duration; t_e – Expected duration; σ – Standard deviation; σ^2 – Variance

The duration of each activity is defined by three time estimates according to the PERT method: optimistic, most likely, and pessimistic durations, as shown in Table 1.

Next, each duration is replaced with a triangular fuzzy number, as shown in Table 2. For each activity, at least three fuzzy duration estimates are provided. A weighting coefficient is assigned to each estimate so that the sum of all weighting coefficients equals 1.

Finally, the reliable fuzzy duration for each activity is determined using the fuzzy Delphi method, as shown in Table 2. The calculation of the reliable fuzzy duration according to the Delphi method is carried out by computing the average value of the proposed estimates for each activity using formula 8 (Habibi et al., 2018).

$$Ft_{p,i}(a_{p,i}, b_{p,i}, c_{p,i}) = \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j * a_{j,i}}{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j}, \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j * b_{j,i}}{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j}, \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j * c_{j,i}}{\sum_{j=1}^m w_j} \right) \quad (8)$$

Where is:

$Ft_{p,i}(a_{p,i}, b_{p,i}, c_{p,i})$

Reliable fuzzy duration of activity “i”

w_j

The weight coefficients assigned to each estimate of the fuzzy duration of activity “i”

$j = 1, \dots, m$

The number of fuzzy duration estimates

$Ft_j(a_j, b_j, c_j)$

Fuzzy duration of activity i for each estimate $j = 1, \dots, m$

Table 2: Reliable fuzzy activity duration

Activity	PA	NA	w_j	Fuzzy duration			Reliable fuzzy duration Ft_i		
				a	b	c	a	b	c
1		2,3,4	$w_1= 0.2$	2	4	6	3.1	5.1	6.8
			$w_2= 0.5$	3	5	7			
			$w_3= 0.3$	4	6	7			
2	1	5	$w_1= 0.2$	2	4	6	2.8	4.5	6.3
			$w_2= 0.5$	3	5	6			
			$w_3= 0.3$	3	4	7			
3	1	7	$w_1= 0.2$	8	12	16	10.2	13.9	17.3
			$w_2= 0.5$	10	14	18			
			$w_3= 0.3$	12	15	17			
4	1	6	$w_1= 0.2$	2	3	4	3.1	4.1	5.1
			$w_2= 0.5$	3	4	5			
			$w_3= 0.3$	4	5	6			
5	2	8	$w_1= 0.2$	5	7	9	5.5	8	9.5
			$w_2= 0.5$	6	9	10			
			$w_3= 0.3$	5	7	9			
6	4	7	$w_1= 0.2$	2	4	8	2.8	4.5	6.9
			$w_2= 0.5$	3	5	7			
			$w_3= 0.3$	3	4	6			
7	3,6	3,6	$w_1= 0.2$	7	10	13	8.3	11.1	12.8
			$w_2= 0.5$	9	11	12			
			$w_3= 0.3$	8	12	14			
8	5	5	$w_1= 0.2$	2	4	5	2.5	4.5	5.5
			$w_2= 0.5$	3	5	6			
			$w_3= 0.3$	2	4	5			
9	7,8	7,8	$w_1= 0.2$	9	13	15	10.3	13.8	16.9
			$w_2= 0.5$	11	14	17			
			$w_3= 0.3$	10	14	18			
10	9		$w_1= 0.2$	5	7	8	6.9	8.9	11.5
			$w_2= 0.5$	7	9	12			
			$w_3= 0.3$	8	10	13			

In the second phase of the experiment, it is necessary to determine the Critical Degree (CD) of each path in the network diagram and of each activity, i.e., to identify the critical path.

To determine the Critical Degree (CD) for each path in the network diagram, it is first necessary to assign reliable fuzzy durations to all activities using triangular fuzzy numbers, based on the results from the first phase of the experiment, as shown in Table 2. After that, a forward pass calculation is performed to determine the early start and early finish times for each activity, expressed as triangular fuzzy numbers. In this way, the fuzzy project duration is also determined (see Table 3).

Table 3: Calculation of Fuzzy Early Start and Fuzzy Early Finish of Activities

Activities	PA	NA	Reliable fuzzy duration Ft_i	Fuzzy Early Start FES_i	Fuzzy Early Finish FEF_i
1		2,3,4	(3.1; 5.1; 6.8)	(0;0;0)	(3.1; 5.1; 6.8)
2	1	5	(2.8; 4.5; 6.3)	(3.1; 5.1; 6.8)	(5.9; 9.6; 13.1)
3	1	7	(10.2; 13.9; 17.3)	(3.1; 5.1; 6.8)	(13.3; 19.0; 24.1)
4	1	6	(3.1; 4.1; 5.1)	(3.1; 5.1; 6.8)	(6.2; 9.2; 11.9)
5	2	8	(5.5; 8.0; 9.5)	(5.9; 9.6; 13.1)	(11.4; 17.6; 22.6)
6	4	7	(2.8; 4.5; 6.9)	(6.2; 9.2; 11.9)	(9.0; 13.7; 18.8)
7	3,6	9	(8.3; 11.1; 12.8)	(13.3; 19.0; 24.1)	(21.6; 30.1; 36.9)
8	5	9	(2.5; 4.5; 5.5)	(11.4; 17.6; 22.6)	(13.9; 22.1; 28.1)
9	7,8	10	(10.3; 13.8; 16.9)	(21.6; 30.1; 36.9)	(31.9; 43.9; 53.8)
10	9		(6.9; 8.9; 11.5)	(31.9; 43.9; 53.8)	(38.8; 52.8; 65.3)

$$FES_i = \max[FEF(PA)] \tag{9}$$

$$FEF_i = \max[FEF(PA) + Ft_i] \tag{10}$$

Where is:

FEF(PA) - Fuzzy early finish of the predecessor activity

Now it is necessary to determine the fuzzy duration for each path in the network, i.e., for each path in the network diagram, the path length is determined using a triangular fuzzy number, as shown in Table 4. Then, for each path in the network diagram, the “crisp” (deterministic) duration, i.e., the “crisp” length of each path DPL_k , is determined (Ammar & Abd-El Khalek, 2019). This is done by defuzzification using the center of area (centroid) method COA, i.e., by converting the fuzzy (uncertain) number into a deterministic (clear) number using the COA method, according to formula (6). In the same way, the “crisp” (deterministic) project duration DPD is determined, and the values are shown in Table 4.

Then, according to Ammar and Abd-El Khalek (2019), the following indicators are calculated for each path in the network diagram: Crisp path ratio – DPR_k , Intersection ratio – IR_{kp} , Critical Degree Index – CD_k

$$DPR_k = DPL_k / DPD \tag{11}$$

Where is:

DPL_k Crisp length of the k-th path in the network diagram

DPD Crisp project duration

$$IR_{kp} = \begin{cases} \frac{c_k - a_p}{c_p - a_p}, & \text{if } c_k > a_p \\ 0 & \text{if } c_k \leq a_p \end{cases} \tag{12}$$

$$CD_k = DPR_k \times IR_{kp} \tag{13}$$

The parameters used in the formula for calculating the intersection ratio IR_{kp} are shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3: The parameters used in the formula for calculating the intersection ratio IR_{kp} (adapted and modified from Ammar and Abd-El Khalek, 2019)

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

Table 4 shows, for each path in the network diagram, the following parameters: DPL_k , DPD , DPR_k , IR_{kp} , and the criticality index CD_k .

Table 4: Fuzzy parameters of the project

Path in the network	FT_k	DPL_k	DP_k	IR_{kp}	CD_k
1-2-5-8-9-10	(31.3; 44.8; 56.5)	44.35	0.8316	0.6423	0.5341
1-3-7-9-10	(38.8; 52.8; 65.3)	52.42	0.9829	0.9808	0.9640
1-4-6-7-9-10	(34.5; 47.5; 60.0)	47.37	0.8882	0.7769	0.6900
Project duration	(39.8; 53.8; 65.8)	53.33			

Based on the data from Table 4, it can be concluded that the path 1-3-7-9-10 is most likely critical, as it has the highest criticality index value of $CD_k = 0.9640$. The other paths have lower criticality index values CD_k and are most likely non-critical paths.

5. CONCLUSION

The implementation of any project, from conception to completion, takes place under conditions of varying degrees of uncertainty. Fuzzy logic addresses imprecision or ambiguity in estimation and may be preferable to probability theory in situations where historical data on activity durations are unavailable or unreliable. For this reason, the use of fuzzy set theory is proposed for modeling uncertainty, as an alternative to traditional probabilistic methods. This paper presents a novel methodology for assessing the degree of criticality of project paths and activities within a fuzzy logic framework. In the proposed methodology, the relative degree of criticality and the agreement index are integrated into a unified indicator to provide a more precise and comprehensive measure of criticality. The research results have shown that the fuzzy adaptive CPM-PERT method can be successfully applied in project planning. It is particularly suitable for use in the construction industry, due to the high degree of subjectivity in estimating activity durations and costs..

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